

Revealing the Variational Dynamics of Brain Order–Chaos Reorganization Using a Hurst–Hilbert–Huang Framework

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Abstract

The analysis of electroencephalographic (EEG) activity has historically been dominated by linear approaches centred on spectral decomposition and the quantification of signal power within predefined frequency bands. While these methods have played a fundamental role in the development of contemporary neuroscience, they exhibit important limitations when applied to nonlinear, non-stationary, and highly complex systems such as the human brain.

In this work, a new methodological framework is introduced, based on the combined use of the Hurst exponent and the Hilbert–Huang Transform, hereafter referred to as the Hurst–Hilbert–Huang (HHH) framework. The proposed approach begins with the local estimation of the Hurst exponent over band-filtered EEG signals, yielding a derived time series that captures the temporal evolution of the system’s order–chaos balance. This second-order time series is subsequently analysed using the Hilbert–Huang Transform, allowing for a time–frequency representation that does not correspond to classical neuronal oscillations.

Instead, the HHH spectrogram enables the visualisation of **the variational dynamics of the frequency of reorganisation of the brain order–chaos balance**, an emergent, second-order observable that cannot be accessed through traditional spectral or wavelet-based methods (Hurst, 1951; Huang et al., 1998; Díaz & Córdova, 2021).

Representative results obtained from multichannel EEG recordings during a visual reasoning task are presented, revealing structured, reproducible spatio-temporal patterns across cortical regions, as well as systematic differences between low-beta and high-beta activity. Finally, a set of quantitative descriptors derived from the HHH spectrogram is proposed, organised into an individual dynamic profile of the brain order–chaos balance.

Keywords: EEG, order and chaos, Hurst exponent, brain entropy, Hilbert–Huang, complex systems.

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1. Introduction

Since the earliest electroencephalographic recordings, EEG signals have been interpreted primarily as the superposition of electrical oscillations whose organisation can be described through linear spectral tools, such as the Fast Fourier Transform and, more recently, wavelet-based methods. These approaches have enabled the association of specific frequency bands with distinct neurophysiological and cognitive states and have become standard in both experimental and clinical practice.

However, the brain is not a linear or stationary system, but rather a complex dynamical system operating far from equilibrium, characterised by nonlinearity, self-organisation, long-range temporal correlations, and continuous transitions between different functional regimes. Within this context, spectral power constitutes an inherently limited descriptor, as it captures neither the internal organisation of neural activity nor the dynamics governing transitions between ordered and disordered states (Díaz et al., 2015).

A growing body of theoretical and empirical work suggests that the brain operates near the edge of chaos, dynamically balancing order and disorder in a manner that supports both stability and adaptability (Beggs & Plenz, 2003; Díaz & Córdova, 2021). From this perspective, cognitive processing is not adequately described solely in terms of oscillatory activity within fixed frequency bands, but rather emerges from the continuous regulation of the system's internal dynamical regime.

In this context, the present work proposes a derived analytical framework that does not focus on EEG electrical frequencies per se, but instead on the characterisation of the temporal scales associated with the dynamic reorganisation of the brain order–chaos balance. By shifting the level of analysis from first-order signal properties to second-order dynamical descriptors, the Hurst–Hilbert–Huang framework opens a new observational window onto the functional organisation of brain activity, whose theoretical foundations and methodological implementation are developed in the sections that follow.

2. Theoretical framework

2.1 Order, Chaos, and Complexity in Brain Activity

Within the framework of dynamical systems theory, order and chaos are not mutually exclusive states but rather represent the extremes of a continuous spectrum of dynamical regimes. At one extreme, purely random processes—such as white noise—correspond to states of maximal entropy and minimal temporal correlation. At the other, highly ordered systems are characterised by rigid, predictable dynamics that severely constrain adaptability. Complex systems capable of sustained functionality in changing environments tend to operate in intermediate regimes, where order and disorder coexist in a balanced manner.

The brain constitutes a paradigmatic example of such a complex, self-organising system. A growing body of theoretical and empirical evidence suggests that neural activity exhibits scale invariance, long-range temporal correlations, and self-similar structures across multiple temporal and spatial scales (Mandelbrot & Van Ness, 1968; Beggs & Plenz, 2003). These properties are incompatible with purely linear or stationary descriptions and instead point towards a dynamical organisation governed by continuous transitions between more ordered and more disordered states.

From this perspective, brain function cannot be adequately characterised by static descriptors alone. Rather, it emerges from the ongoing regulation of the system's internal dynamical regime, through which stability and flexibility are jointly maintained. The balance between order and chaos thus constitutes a fundamental dimension of brain dynamics, whose characterisation requires observables capable of capturing both temporal organisation and its evolution over time.

2.2 The Hurst exponent as an observable of the order–chaos balance

The Hurst exponent was originally introduced in the context of hydrology as a quantitative measure of long-term temporal dependence in time series (Hurst, 1951). Subsequently, it has been shown to provide a robust descriptor of memory effects, self-similarity, and persistence properties in a wide range of natural and artificial systems. In particular, the Hurst exponent allows one to distinguish between persistent ($H > 0.5$), uncorrelated ($H = 0.5$), and anti-persistent ($H < 0.5$) temporal dynamics.

In the context of EEG analysis, the Hurst exponent has been employed as a nonlinear estimator of the degree of temporal organisation present in neural signals (Díaz et al., 2019). Unlike spectral power, which quantifies the amplitude of oscillatory components at specific frequencies, the Hurst exponent captures how past fluctuations influence future dynamics, thereby providing direct information about the system's internal regulatory structure.

Importantly, recent studies have shown that anti-persistent values of the Hurst exponent ($H < 0.5$) should not be interpreted as mere noise or randomness. On the contrary, such values reflect the presence of active regulatory mechanisms that constrain runaway dynamics and promote stability through negative feedback processes. From this viewpoint, anti-persistence constitutes an expression of complex homeostatic stability rather than disorder, particularly in systems operating near criticality (Díaz & Córdova, 2021).

Accordingly, the Hurst exponent can be interpreted as an observable of the brain order–chaos balance, reflecting the position of the system along the continuum between excessive regularity and unstructured randomness. Its estimation over time therefore provides access to the dynamics of this balance, rather than to a static characterisation alone.

2.3 Meta-dynamics and second-order oscillations

A crucial aspect of the Hurst exponent in the context of brain dynamics is that it does not remain constant over time. When estimated locally over consecutive temporal windows, the Hurst exponent itself exhibits fluctuations that reflect changes in the underlying dynamical regime of the system. These fluctuations give rise to what can be described as a meta-dynamic or second-order dynamic, superimposed on the first-order dynamics of the EEG signal.

This second-order dynamic does not correspond to oscillatory activity in the electrophysiological sense. Rather, it reflects the temporal evolution of the system's internal organisation, that is, the manner in which the balance between order and chaos is continuously regulated. In this sense, the oscillations observed in the locally estimated Hurst exponent represent transitions between different regimes of temporal organisation, rather than changes in electrical activity per se (Díaz et al., 2019).

The study of this meta-dynamic requires analytical tools capable of accommodating nonlinearity, non-stationarity, and adaptivity, without imposing predefined basis functions or global assumptions about the signal structure. Traditional spectral methods are ill-suited to

this task, as they are designed to analyse first-order oscillatory components. By contrast, approaches that explicitly target the dynamics of derived, second-order signals are required in order to characterise the temporal structure of order–chaos regulation in brain activity.

3. Methodology

3.1 Experimental conditions and EEG acquisition

EEG recordings were obtained from healthy adult subjects during the execution of a visual reasoning task, with a duration ranging between approximately 3 and 5 minutes. The experimental protocol and task design correspond to those described in previous studies and were selected in order to elicit sustained cognitive engagement without inducing excessive fatigue (Díaz et al., 2015).

Signals were acquired using a 14-channel EEG system, with electrodes positioned according to the international 10–20 system (AF3–AF4, F7–F8, F3–F4, FC5–FC6, T7–T8, P7–P8, O1–O2). The sampling frequency was set to 128 Hz, providing sufficient temporal resolution for the subsequent estimation of local dynamical properties. All recordings were conducted under controlled laboratory conditions.

3.2 Pre-processing and band filtering

Raw EEG signals were first subjected to standard pre-processing procedures, including artefact removal, baseline correction, and amplitude normalisation. These steps were implemented in order to minimise the influence of non-neural components and inter-channel variability on the subsequent analysis.

Following pre-processing, the signals were band-pass filtered into two sub-bands of interest: low beta (13–21 Hz) and high beta (22–30 Hz). This subdivision was motivated by previous findings showing systematic differences in entropic and dynamical properties between these sub-bands, as well as their relevance for cognitive processing and executive control (Díaz et al., 2022). All filtering operations were performed using zero-phase digital filters to avoid phase distortions.

3.3 Local estimation of the Hurst exponent

Each band-filtered EEG signal was segmented into consecutive, non-overlapping windows of 128 samples, corresponding to 1 second of the original EEG recording. For each window, the Hurst exponent was estimated using rescaled-range (R/S) analysis, yielding a sequence of successive Hurst values.

This procedure generated a new time series, denoted $H(t)$, which represents the temporal evolution of the order–chaos balance of the EEG signal at a local scale (Hurst, 1951; Díaz & Córdova, 2021). Importantly, this series does not describe electrical activity directly, but rather encodes the dynamical regime of the underlying process, as expressed through its persistence properties.

3.4 Hurst–Hilbert–Huang transform

The time series $H(t)$, explicitly considered as a second-order signal describing the temporal evolution of the system’s dynamical regime, was subsequently analysed using the Hilbert–Huang Transform. This procedure consists of two main steps: Empirical Mode Decomposition (EMD) followed by the application of the Hilbert transform to each intrinsic mode function (IMF).

Through EMD, the signal $H(t)$ was decomposed into a finite set of IMFs that capture oscillatory modes intrinsic to the data, without imposing any a priori basis functions or assumptions of stationarity. The Hilbert transform was then applied to each IMF in order to obtain their instantaneous amplitude and instantaneous frequency, yielding a time–frequency representation known as the HHH spectrogram (Huang et al., 1998; Córdova et al., 2022).

It is important to emphasise that the frequencies obtained through this procedure do not correspond to EEG frequencies in the classical electrophysiological sense. Instead, they represent temporal scales associated with the reorganisation dynamics of the brain order–chaos balance. The formal definition of these quantities, along with their mathematical interpretation and units, is provided in Appendix A.

4. Results

4.1. Multichannel HHH Spectrograms

Figure 1. Hurst–Hilbert–Huang (HHH) spectrograms of 14 EEG channels during a visual reasoning task. The two columns on the left correspond to low beta and the two columns on the right correspond to high beta. In each case, homologous electrodes from the left and right hemisphere are shown.

Figure 1 presents representative Hurst–Hilbert–Huang (HHH) spectrograms obtained from the 14 EEG channels during the execution of the visual reasoning task. The spectrograms are organised by hemisphere and by beta sub-band, with low-beta activity displayed on the left columns and high-beta activity on the right columns.

At a global level, all HHH spectrograms exhibit clearly non-random time–frequency structures, characterised by the presence of persistent bands predominantly concentrated at low HHH frequencies. These structures are consistently observed across channels and across hemispheres, indicating that the detected patterns reflect intrinsic properties of the system rather than artefacts introduced by the estimation procedure or by local signal fluctuations.

The contrast between regions of higher and lower spectral intensity further suggests that the reorganisation dynamics of the order–chaos balance occur in a structured and intermittent manner, rather than as a homogeneous or stationary process over time.

4.2 Differentiation between low-beta and high-beta activity

Systematic differences are observed between the HHH spectrograms corresponding to low-beta and high-beta EEG activity. Low-beta spectrograms tend to exhibit smoother, more continuous structures, with relatively narrow effective bandwidths and lower mean reorganisation frequencies.

In contrast, high-beta spectrograms display increased temporal fragmentation, broader effective bandwidths, and higher average HHH frequencies. These features indicate a faster and more complex reorganisation regime, consistent with increased cognitive demand and enhanced adaptive regulation during task performance (Díaz et al., 2022).

Importantly, these differences do not reflect variations in beta-band power, but rather changes in the dynamics of the underlying order–chaos balance, as captured by the second-order HHH representation.

4.3 Spatial organisation and frontal–occipital gradient

Analysis of the spatial distribution of the HHH spectrograms reveals a consistent anterior–posterior gradient. Frontal regions exhibit higher mean HHH frequencies and greater dynamic diversity than parietal and occipital regions, particularly in the high-beta band.

Occipital channels, by contrast, tend to show more stable and slower reorganisation dynamics, with spectral content concentrated at lower HHH frequencies. This pattern is consistent with sustained sensory processing, which requires relative stability rather than rapid reconfiguration.

The frontal–occipital gradient is observed across both hemispheres and across subjects, suggesting that it reflects a fundamental aspect of cortical functional organisation rather than task-specific or individual variability (Díaz & Córdova, 2021).

4.4 Inter-hemispheric symmetry and functional specialisation

At the inter-hemispheric level, the HHH spectrograms exhibit a high degree of global symmetry, particularly in the low-beta band. Homologous channels across hemispheres display similar spectral structures, indicating coordinated regulation of the order–chaos balance at the whole-brain level.

Nevertheless, under high-beta conditions, subtle but systematic inter-hemispheric differences emerge, especially in frontal regions. These micro-asymmetries are reflected in differences in reorganisation frequency and dynamic bandwidth, suggesting fine-grained functional specialisation under increased cognitive load.

Such patterns are consistent with models of cooperative inter-hemispheric processing, in which global symmetry is preserved while allowing localised differentiation in response to task demands (Beggs & Plenz, 2003; Díaz et al., 2015).

4.5 Individual dynamic profile of the brain order–chaos balance

In order to integrate the graphical and quantitative information provided by the HHH spectrograms, the derived descriptors were organised into an individual dynamic profile of the brain order–chaos balance (Table 1). This profile summarises, for a single subject, key dynamical parameters extracted from the HHH representation, including mean reorganisation frequency, effective bandwidth, overall dynamic intensity, frontal–occipital gradients, and inter-hemispheric symmetry indices.

The individual dynamic profile provides a compact yet comprehensive characterisation of the subject’s functional state during task execution. By focusing on second-order dynamical descriptors rather than first-order signal properties, this representation allows direct

comparison between beta sub-bands, cortical regions, and hemispheres, without relying on assumptions of stationarity or on conventional power-based metrics.

Table 1

Individual dynamic profile of brain order/chaos balance derived from the Hurst–Hilbert–Huang (HHH) spectrogram

Basis of comparison: Intra-subject (between bands, regions and hemispheres)

Panel A. Global descriptors

Descriptor	Low β	High β	Unit	Interpretation
Global HHH centroid (\bar{f}_{HHH})	6.2	9.7	Hz_HHH	Higher mean frequency of order-chaos reorganisation in high- β , indicating faster global adaptive reconfiguration of brain dynamics under increased cognitive demand.
Effective bandwidth (BW_HHH)	3.0	5.5	Hz_HHH	Broader distribution of reorganisation frequencies in high- β , reflecting richer multiscale dynamics and increased flexibility of the underlying regulatory process.
Total HHH energy (E_HHH)	1.00	1.41	norm.	Higher total reorganisation energy in high- β , consistent with greater cognitive load and sustained dynamical engagement during task performance.
Temporal variability (CV)	11%	29%	%	Increased temporal variability of reorganisation dynamics in high- β , suggesting reduced stability and more frequent regime switching under cognitively demanding conditions.

Panel B. Frontal-occipital gradient

Descriptor	Low β	High β	Unit	Interpretation
Frontal centroid (\bar{f}_F)	7.1	11.3	Hz_HHH	Higher frontal reorganisation frequency in high- β , indicating dominant involvement of frontal networks in executive control and adaptive regulation.
Occipital centroid (\bar{f}_O)	5.4	7.6	Hz_HHH	Lower and more stable posterior reorganisation frequency, consistent with sustained sensory processing and reduced need for rapid dynamical reconfiguration.
Frontal-occipital gradient (Δf_{F-O})	1.7	3.7	Hz_HHH	Stronger anterior-posterior gradient in high- β , reflecting increased hierarchical differentiation between executive and sensory regions.
Normalised slope	0.41	0.90	Hz/region	Steeper spatial gradient of reorganisation dynamics, indicating sharper functional organisation under increased cognitive demand.

Panel C. Interhemispheric symmetry

Descriptor	Low β	High β	Unit	Interpretation
Left hemisphere energy (E_L)	0.51	0.59	norm.	Higher relative reorganisation energy in the left hemisphere, especially in high- β , reflecting enhanced adaptive cognitive regulation.
Right hemisphere energy (E_R)	0.49	0.41	norm.	Lower reorganisation energy in the right hemisphere under high- β , consistent with a more stable dynamical regime during task performance.
Energy symmetry index (SI_E)	0.02	0.18	adim.	Emergent functional micro-asymmetries in high- β conditions.
Centroid difference $ \bar{f}_L - \bar{f}_R $	0.3	1.4	Hz_HHH	Faster left frontal reorganisation dynamics relative to the right hemisphere.

Panel D. Regional dynamic profile

Region	\bar{f}_{HHH} Low β	\bar{f}_{HHH} High β	BW_HHH High β	Interpretation
Frontal	7.0	11.1	6.2	Marked increase in reorganisation frequency and bandwidth, indicating strong executive control engagement and high adaptive flexibility under cognitive demand.
Temporal	6.2	9.5	5.4	Intermediate reorganisation dynamics, consistent with multisensory integration and context-dependent adaptive processing.
Parietal	5.9	8.8	4.9	Moderate reorganisation dynamics, supporting visuospatial coordination and sensorimotor integration processes.
Occipital	5.2	7.4	3.5	Lower and more stable reorganisation dynamics, reflecting sustained sensory processing and reduced need for rapid adaptive reconfiguration.

Table 1. Individual dynamic profile of the brain order/chaos balance derived from the Hurst–Hilbert–Huang (HHH) spectrogram. Subject: S01- Experimental condition: Visual reasoning task (≈ 4 min) EEG bands: Low beta (13–21 Hz), High beta (22–30 Hz). The interhemispheric difference of the HHH centroid is defined as $|\bar{f}_L - \bar{f}_R|$, where, and correspond to the HHH spectral centroids averaged in the left and right hemispheres, respectively (see Appendix A).

Table 1 integrates the quantitative descriptors derived from HHH (spectral centroid, effective bandwidth, total energy, frontal-occipital gradient and interhemispheric symmetry indices), formally defined in Appendix A, allowing a quantitative and integrated characterization of the dynamic state of the brain of the subject analyzed.

In order to complement this quantitative characterisation, an interpretative framework for the evaluative reading of individual HHH profiles is provided in Appendix B. This appendix illustrates how the proposed descriptors may be jointly interpreted in terms of adaptive regulation, balance between order and chaos, and functional organisation, without implying clinical diagnosis.

5. Discussion

The Hurst–Hilbert–Huang framework introduced in this work provides access to a dimension of brain dynamics that has remained largely unobservable through conventional EEG analysis techniques: **the variational dynamics of the frequency of reorganisation of the brain order–chaos balance**. Crucially, this dynamic does not correspond to neuronal oscillations in the electrophysiological sense, nor to variations in spectral power within predefined frequency bands. Rather, it reflects the temporal modulation of the scales at which the brain actively reorganises its internal dynamical regime.

From this perspective, the HHH spectrogram constitutes a new representational space for EEG analysis. Instead of depicting the distribution of signal energy across frequencies, it reveals how the system transitions between regimes of greater and lesser temporal persistence, thereby capturing the meta-dynamics of order–chaos regulation. This distinction is essential, as it separates first-order signal properties from second-order organisational dynamics, which cannot be inferred directly from the original EEG signal or from its classical time–frequency representations.

The results presented in this study demonstrate that the dynamics of order–chaos reorganisation are neither random nor spatially homogeneous. On the contrary, they exhibit robust, reproducible time–frequency structures and clear patterns of spatial organisation. The systematic differentiation observed between low-beta and high-beta activity suggests that

distinct cognitive states are associated with specific regimes of dynamic reorganisation, characterised by differences in reorganisation speed, bandwidth, and variability (Díaz et al., 2022).

The presence of a consistent frontal–occipital gradient further indicates that the regulation of the order–chaos balance is hierarchically organised across the cortex. Frontal regions, particularly under increased cognitive demand, display higher reorganisation frequencies and greater dynamic diversity, consistent with their role in executive control and adaptive regulation. In contrast, occipital regions maintain slower and more stable reorganisation dynamics, in line with sustained sensory processing requirements (Díaz & Córdova, 2021).

At the inter-hemispheric level, the results reveal a combination of global symmetry and localised differentiation. While overall symmetry is largely preserved—especially in the low-beta band—subtle functional asymmetries emerge under high-beta conditions, primarily in frontal areas. These micro-asymmetries do not indicate unilateral dominance, but rather reflect fine-grained specialisation within a cooperative inter-hemispheric framework, as predicted by models of distributed cortical processing (Beggs & Plenz, 2003; Díaz et al., 2015).

Taken together, these findings support the view that the brain operates near a critical regime, continuously adjusting the frequency and complexity of its internal reorganisation in response to cognitive demands. The Hurst–Hilbert–Huang framework provides, for the first time, a methodological tool capable of directly visualising and quantifying this meta-dynamic process, thereby opening a new avenue for the investigation of brain complexity and functional organisation.

Beyond its methodological contribution, the proposed HHH framework also opens the possibility for an evaluative reading of individual dynamical profiles, as illustrated in Appendix B. By characterising how the brain regulates the balance between order and chaos across spatial and spectral scales, this approach provides a principled basis for exploring adaptive efficiency and functional organisation, without presupposing clinical categorisation.

6. Conclusions

In this work, a new methodological framework for the time–frequency analysis of the brain order–chaos balance in EEG signals has been presented. By combining local estimation of the Hurst exponent with the Hilbert–Huang Transform, the proposed Hurst–Hilbert–Huang approach enables the construction of a derived, second-order signal whose analysis reveals dynamical properties that are not accessible through conventional EEG methodologies.

The central contribution of this framework lies in the identification and characterisation of **the variational dynamics of the frequency of reorganisation of the brain order–chaos balance**. This dynamic, which had neither been explicitly detected nor visualised in previous studies, constitutes a new observable of brain function, reflecting how the system actively regulates its internal dynamical regime over time.

The results demonstrate that this reorganisation dynamic is structured, reproducible, and spatially differentiated, allowing for the identification of systematic differences between low-beta and high-beta activity, cortical gradients along the frontal–occipital axis, and patterns of inter-hemispheric symmetry and fine-grained functional specialisation. By organising these descriptors into an individual dynamic profile, the proposed framework provides a compact yet informative representation of the functional state of the brain under cognitive engagement.

Importantly, the Hurst–Hilbert–Huang framework is not intended to replace traditional spectral or wavelet-based EEG analysis techniques. Rather, it complements them by incorporating a meta-dynamic level of description that captures the regulation of the brain’s own order–chaos balance. In this sense, the present work establishes the conceptual, methodological, and formal foundations for a new line of research focused on the study of brain complexity through second-order dynamical observables (Díaz et al., 2015; Díaz et al., 2022).

Finally, the interpretative framework outlined in Appendix B illustrates how the proposed descriptors may support future evaluative and translational studies, particularly in contexts where individual differences in adaptive regulation are of interest.

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Appendix A

Mathematical formalism of the Hurst–Hilbert–Huang framework

This appendix presents the complete mathematical formalism underlying the Hurst–Hilbert–Huang (HHH) framework, including the definition of variables, derived signals, and quantitative descriptors used throughout the manuscript. Its purpose is to provide a precise and unambiguous specification of the analytical model, independent of graphical representations.

A.1 Local estimation of the Hurst exponent

Let $x(t)$ denote a band-filtered EEG signal, sampled at frequency f_s . The signal is segmented into consecutive, non-overlapping temporal windows of fixed length N , corresponding to a duration $\Delta t = N/f_s$.

For each window, the Hurst exponent H is estimated using rescaled-range (R/S) analysis (Hurst, 1951). Given a windowed signal x_i , $i = 1, \dots, N$, the cumulative deviation series is defined as:

$$Y(k) = \sum_{i=1}^k (x_i - \bar{x}), k = 1, \dots, N,$$

where \bar{x} is the mean value of the signal within the window. The range $R(N)$ and the standard deviation $S(N)$ are given by:

$$R(N) = \max_{1 \leq k \leq N} Y(k) - \min_{1 \leq k \leq N} Y(k),$$

$$S(N) = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (x_i - \bar{x})^2}.$$

The rescaled range satisfies the asymptotic relation:

$$\frac{R(N)}{S(N)} \sim N^H,$$

from which the Hurst exponent H is estimated as the slope of the linear fit in log–log coordinates.

A.2 Construction of the second-order signal $H(t)$

By applying the local estimation procedure over successive windows, a new time series is obtained:

$$H(t_j), j = 1, 2, \dots, M,$$

where each value $H(t_j)$ represents the estimated Hurst exponent within the j -th temporal window. This series constitutes a **second-order signal**, in the sense that it does not describe electrical activity directly, but rather the temporal evolution of the persistence properties of the original EEG signal.

The values of $H(t)$ lie in the interval $(0, 1)$ and encode the instantaneous balance between persistence and anti-persistence, which is interpreted as the balance between order and chaos in the underlying dynamical process.

A.3 Empirical Mode Decomposition of $H(t)$

The second-order signal $H(t)$ is analysed using Empirical Mode Decomposition (EMD), which decomposes the signal into a finite set of intrinsic mode functions (IMFs):

$$H(t) = \sum_{k=1}^K \text{IMF}_k(t) + r(t),$$

where $\text{IMF}_k(t)$ are oscillatory components satisfying the EMD conditions, and $r(t)$ is the residual trend.

Each IMF represents an intrinsic oscillatory mode of the second-order signal, corresponding to a specific temporal scale of variation in the order–chaos balance.

A.4 Hilbert transform and instantaneous frequency

The Hilbert transform is applied to each intrinsic mode function $\text{IMF}_k(t)$ to construct its analytic signal:

$$z_k(t) = \text{IMF}_k(t) + i \mathcal{H}[\text{IMF}_k(t)] = A_k(t)e^{i\phi_k(t)},$$

where $A_k(t)$ is the instantaneous amplitude, $\phi_k(t)$ is the instantaneous phase, and $\mathcal{H}[\cdot]$ denotes the Hilbert transform.

The instantaneous frequency is then defined as:

$$f_k(t) = \frac{1}{2\pi} \frac{d\phi_k(t)}{dt}.$$

The set of instantaneous frequencies $f_k(t)$ constitutes the frequency axis of the HHH spectrogram.

A.5 Interpretation of HHH frequencies

It is essential to emphasise that the frequencies obtained through the HHH framework:

$$f_{HHH} \neq f_{EEG},$$

that is, they do not correspond to electrophysiological EEG frequencies. Instead, f_{HHH} represents the **frequency of reorganisation of the order–chaos balance**, namely the rate at which the system transitions between regimes of greater and lesser temporal persistence.

Thus, the HHH spectrogram visualises the temporal dynamics of this reorganisation process, rather than oscillatory neural activity.

A.6 Quantitative descriptors derived from the HHH spectrogram

From the HHH spectrogram, several quantitative descriptors are defined:

- **Mean reorganisation frequency**

$$\bar{f}_{HHH} = \frac{1}{T} \int f_{HHH}(t) dt$$

- **Effective bandwidth**

Defined as the standard deviation of $f_{HHH}(t)$, representing the diversity of reorganisation scales.

- **Total HHH energy**

Obtained as the integral of instantaneous amplitudes over time and frequency.

- **Frontal–occipital gradient**

Defined as the difference between mean reorganisation frequencies in frontal and occipital regions.

- **Inter-hemispheric symmetry index**

Quantifying the relative difference in HHH descriptors between homologous channels in both hemispheres.

All descriptors are computed separately for low-beta and high-beta conditions and are reported in dimensionless units or in units of Hz_{HHH} , explicitly distinguishing them from EEG frequencies.

A.7 Summary

The Hurst–Hilbert–Huang framework constitutes a multi-stage analytical model in which a first-order EEG signal is transformed into a second-order dynamical representation, whose time–frequency analysis reveals the variational dynamics of the brain order–chaos balance. This appendix provides the formal basis required for the reproducibility, interpretation, and extension of the method.

Appendix B

Interpretative framework for the evaluative reading of individual order–chaos balance profiles

B.1. Conceptual basis: optimal brain functioning at the edge of chaos

Complex adaptive systems are known to operate most efficiently in a narrow regime located at the transition between order and chaos. In this region, often referred to as the *edge of chaos*, the system maintains sufficient stability to preserve functional organisation while retaining enough flexibility to reorganise in response to internal or external perturbations. It is precisely within this regime that structured attractors emerge, enabling coordinated yet adaptable dynamics.

In the context of brain function, excessive order may manifest as rigid, over constrained dynamics with reduced responsiveness and limited capacity for reconfiguration. Conversely, excessive chaos may lead to unstable, poorly coordinated activity, impairing the integration of distributed processes. Optimal cognitive and adaptive performance is therefore expected to arise from a dynamically regulated balance between these two extremes, rather than from either pole in isolation.

The Hurst–Hilbert–Huang (HHH) framework introduced in this work is explicitly designed to characterise this balance, not at the level of raw electrical activity, but at the level of the *dynamics governing the reorganisation of the order–chaos regime itself*.

B.2. Dynamic equilibrium and adaptive reorganisation

From a dynamical systems perspective, the brain can be understood as a continuously self-regulating system that responds to perturbations—such as sensory input, cognitive demands, or internal fluctuations—by transiently departing from a given equilibrium state and subsequently converging towards a new dynamic configuration.

Crucially, this equilibrium is not static. Rather, it constitutes a metastable state, temporarily stabilised yet intrinsically prepared for further reorganisation. The ability to rapidly and efficiently transition between such equilibria is a hallmark of adaptive brain function.

Within the HHH framework, this capacity is reflected in the **variational dynamics of the frequency of reorganisation of the brain order–chaos balance**. Higher reorganisation frequencies, broader bandwidths, and controlled temporal variability indicate a system actively exploring its dynamical landscape, whereas excessively narrow or excessively diffuse patterns may suggest suboptimal regulation.

B.3. Interpretative reading of the HHH diagnostic profile

The individual HHH diagnostic profile, summarised in Panels A–D, provides a multidimensional characterisation of this regulatory capacity. While the specific numerical values are context-dependent, their relative configuration allows for an evaluative reading along the following dimensions.

B.3.1. Global descriptors (Panel A)

Global measures such as the mean reorganisation frequency, effective bandwidth, total reorganisation energy, and temporal variability offer an overview of the system’s overall dynamical regime.

- **Low mean frequency and narrow bandwidth** may indicate overly ordered dynamics, suggestive of rigidity and reduced adaptability.
- **Very high mean frequency combined with excessive variability** may reflect unstable or poorly constrained reorganisation.
- **Intermediate values**, particularly when accompanied by moderate variability, are consistent with efficient regulation near the edge of chaos.

B.3.2. Frontal–occipital gradient (Panel B)

The anterior–posterior gradient captures the hierarchical organisation of reorganisation dynamics across cortical regions.

- An **excessively steep gradient** may indicate overdominance of executive control mechanisms at the expense of sensory integration.
- A **flattened gradient** may suggest reduced functional differentiation and diminished hierarchical structure.

- A **moderate, well-defined gradient** reflects balanced interaction between executive and sensory systems, supporting flexible yet coordinated processing.

B.3.3. Interhemispheric symmetry (Panel C)

Interhemispheric descriptors quantify the balance between bilateral coordination and functional differentiation.

- **Extreme asymmetries** may point to dysregulated lateralisation or compensatory mechanisms.
- **Perfect symmetry**, while intuitively appealing, may in fact indicate insufficient functional specialisation.
- **Controlled micro-asymmetries**, particularly when dynamically modulated, are consistent with healthy differentiation within an integrated system.

B.3.4. Regional dynamic profile (Panel D)

Regional descriptors reveal how different cortical areas contribute to the global balance of order and chaos.

- **Frontal regions** exhibiting high reorganisation frequency and bandwidth are typically associated with executive control and adaptive regulation.
- **Temporal and parietal regions** often display intermediate dynamics, supporting multisensory integration and spatial coordination.
- **Occipital regions** are expected to show more stable, lower-frequency reorganisation, reflecting sustained sensory processing.

Disruptions to this pattern—such as excessive frontal dominance or abnormally rigid posterior dynamics—may signal suboptimal distribution of regulatory effort.

B.4. Illustrative example: qualitative evaluation of an individual profile

As an illustrative case, the example profile presented in this work exhibits a combination of moderate global reorganisation frequencies, well-defined frontal–occipital gradients, controlled interhemispheric asymmetries, and region-specific dynamics consistent with functional specialisation. Taken together, these features suggest a brain operating near a

dynamically optimal regime, capable of efficient adaptation to cognitive demands while maintaining overall stability.

It is important to emphasise that this evaluative reading is **qualitative and illustrative**, intended to demonstrate the descriptive power of the HHH framework rather than to establish clinical diagnoses.

B.5. Scope and limitations

The interpretative framework outlined here is proposed as a conceptual guide for understanding individual HHH profiles. Its clinical relevance remains to be established through systematic validation studies, including longitudinal designs and correlations with behavioural, cognitive, or clinical measures.

Nonetheless, the framework highlights the potential of second-order dynamical observables—such as the frequency of order–chaos reorganisation—as meaningful descriptors of brain function, opening new avenues for both fundamental and applied research.